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Social Partners' Conceptions of their Role in School-based Initial Vocational Training of Specialists

Mičiulienė, Rita

rita.miciuliene@vdu.lt, Education Academy, Vytautas Magnus University

Abstract

School-based initial vocational education and training (IVET) prevails in some countries, as well as in Lithuania. Within this traditional school setting, companies and enterprises serve as suppliers of internships for school students. This study was aimed to explore the qualitatively different ways in which social partners on the ground (teachers and in-company trainers) experience and understand their roles on initial vocational training of students. A convenience sample of 14 stakeholders from several professional fields were interviewed and phenomenographic data analysis approach was applied. Three conceptions were constructed that described social partners' understanding of their roles in specialists' training. Three dimensions of variation marked the differences among the conceptions: responsibility, interest / benefit and expectations for collaboration. The social partners involved in the training of IVET students have qualitatively similar understating of their roles but unmet expectations about each other's roles and involvement. The results can provide new insights into how the IVET partnership could be designed.

Keywords

social partners, initial vocational education and training, school-based VET, training of specialists

1 Introduction

School-based initial vocational education and training (IVET) prevails in some countries, as well as in Lithuania. Within the traditional school setting, companies and enterprises serve as suppliers of work-based training places – internships – while all regulatory functions – planning, management and control – are concentrated in the VET schools (Rauner & Wittig, 2013). Participation of employer organisations in work-based training process is treated as necessity (Sauli, 2021) leading to the success and accomplishments of the IVET programmes (Peliz et al., 2021; Bakker & Akkerman, 2019). Thus, together with the state and VET schools, employers and their organisations become an important player in the social partnership providing linkage to the labour market (Rauner & Wittig, 2013).

The range of social partners have their own roles, diversity of interests, views and expectations on how a specialist has to be trained for the labour market. The process of reconciliation such interests and views is complicated and challenging (Smak, 2022; Guthrie & Clayton, 2018; Peliz et al., 2021; Martínez-Morales & Marhuenda-Fluixá, 2020; Gîncu & Moldovanu, 2019; Gunbayi, 2015). Lack of mutual trust and differences in views and expectations between different social partners was established in several studies (Ruškus et al.,

2005; Kaminskienė, 2008; Winterton et al., 2008; Maurušaitienė, 2011; Cedefop, 2015; Vaitkute, 2022) usually by analysing IVET social partners' collaboration from the perspective of what is defined by the law. The current study contributes to the existing literature by exploring the perceptions of social partners' views from the "bottom-up" approach.

1.1 Objective

This study is aimed to gain an understanding of key social partners' conceptions of their role and expectations in training qualified specialists for the labour market. In order to contribute to the development of collaboration and social dialogue between social partners, it is important to investigate the qualitative different ways in which they conceptualise their roles in training specialists in IVET demonstrating the extent to which their role is pivotal. This will be done from the point of view of main stakeholders "on the ground": vocational teachers and in-company trainers. While this is not the first study to examine the roles and expectations of the different parties involved in the process, the study contributes to the scarce literature on the discourse of how these social partners conceptualise their roles in school-based IVET.

1.2 Conceptual framework

Role theory, and especially its functional perspective, was applied to explain how the various parties in IVET look at their roles and voice their expectations toward collaboration. According to Biddle (1986), various social structures can be viewed as collections of designated social positions, the shared norms of which govern differentiated behaviours of groups, organizations or communities and individuals belonging to them. "Some of the norms applying to a given position govern general conduct, but others govern only relationships between a focal position and a specific, counter position and among the latter, "roles" are those that apply to the accomplishment of specific functions" (Biddle, 1986, p.70). For example, for vocational schools, the "focal" role is to educate and teach, while, for companies and business organisations – to ensure productivity (Guthrie & Clayton, 2018). Their specific roles within specialist training VET system emerge in the following areas: policy formation, curriculum development and improvement, evaluation and accreditation (Maurušaitienė, 2011). Social partners should participate in all these areas on equal rights and equal shares (Pileičikienė, 2013). However, their roles can differ within each area as they present different possibilities and competences to solve IVET related questions. For example, within curriculum development and improvement area, employers are responsible for identification of present and promising qualification requirements (Gunbayi, 2015) and transferring these into relevant occupational standards. Teachers are responsible for the identification of relevant learning outcomes matching these standards, for the appropriate formulation of statements related to learning outcomes, for the alignment of study content, the share of theoretical and practical training, and other elements, such as infrastructure. Employers, to a greater extend, take responsibility for practical training of IVET students including development of their ethical behaviour, as claimed by Pogorzelska (2013) and Gunbayi (2015).

Roles may reflect normative expectations as well (Biddle, 2013). These can be interpreted as beliefs, preferences or attitudes. For example, some findings about the social partners' expectations show their desire to define their roles better, to facilitate collaboration between school and company (Sauli, 2021); the need for provision of preliminary and underpinning knowledge needed for the job tasks as well as about the contextual specificity of practices (Sappa et al., 2016; Choy & Sappa, 2016), or the preferences to more support learning in the work-based environment (Munangatire & McInerney, 2022; Sappa et al., 2016). As Biddle (1986) explains, each mode of expectation generates roles for somewhat different reasons. Therefore, it is meaningful to expose different role understanding of parties concerned in practical training of students and how these result in either contradictions or collaboration.

1.3 Context

In Lithuania, the role, responsibility, engagement, and importance of social partners and partnership in IVET changed at various stages of development. Historically, two important features have implications for stakeholders' situation in our days: a strong regulatory role of the state and lack of trust within post-totalitarian society (Winterton et al., 2008). In the market economy, the social partners' roles and relationships were defined in the Law on VET in Lithuania (1997) and their functions have been expanded over several years. Despite the social dialog or collaboration between social partners is enshrined in law, and formal rules have been established to ensure that it takes place, social partnership can take largely vary in Lithuanian IVET (Vaitkutė, 2022).

2 Methodology

2.1 Participants and Procedure

Social partners from seven vocational training centres/schools and seven business organizations in Kaunas city, who have experience in practical training of students, organization of practices, cooperation with social partners, participated in the study. Åkerlind (2005) suggests that a sample size in a phenomenography study should be between 10 and 30 participants with a maximum variation (age, gender, education, professional experience, etc.). In total, the sample comprised 14 persons from different occupational fields and different positions, as presented in Table 1. This included six females (VET teachers n=4; in-company trainers n=2) and 8 males (VET teachers n=3, in-company trainers n=5). The duration of their performance as social partners ranged from 4 to 20 years (VET teachers M=15.3 years; in-company trainers M=11,5 years).

Table 1

Distribution of the study participants by role and vocational field

	B-admin.	Hospitality	Helth	Mechanics	Wood	Social service	Total
VET teacher	1	2				1	4
VET head of department			1	1			2
VET Deputy director			1				1
Master-trainer				1	1		2
Instructor			1				1
Personal manager	2						2
Head of the company		1		1			2
Total	3	3	3	3	1	1	14

The data were collected by means of individual semi-structured interviews on the voluntary basis. Due to the pandemic situation, interviews were conducted remotely using IT technology. The leading questions were:

- How do you define your role and responsibility in training a qualified specialist?
- In your opinion, what are or should be the role and responsibilities of the school / company in this process?

To encourage interviewers some other questions were added, for example, "Could you describe your experience in practical training of VET students / trainees? How is your experience in collaborating with partner-part?" All they were recorded and transcribed verbatim in its entirety.

2.2 Data analysis

The data analysis was conducted by adopting the phenomenographic procedure (Åkerlind, 2005) to respond to research question. According to Sappa & Aprea (2014), the main aim of this procedure is to light the qualitative differences in how people understand and experience a specific phenomenon. The main result of a phenomenographic analysis is a number of qualitatively different meanings or ways of experiencing the phenomenon (called “conceptions”) (Sappa & Aprea, 2014, p. 322). In this study, the phenomenon under experiencing was the role of social partners. The conceptions were organized in a hierarchical way moving from the most perceived and assumed role to the least one. Next, the ways of experiencing social partner role in terms of the aspects that appeared to be most important for both grouping together and distinguishing the varying ways of understanding was analysed. It has to be noted that what varies is not the expected roles of the social partners regarding practical training, but it is the way they experience these roles that vary (Munangature & McInerney, 2022). As Marton & Booth (1997, cited in Åkerlind, 2005) argue, that ways of experiencing represent a relationship between the experiencer and the phenomenon being experienced based on the critical (or “key”) aspects of the phenomena they are focusing on. In this study, the focus was on the role performance of each stakeholder: how the role of one stakeholder is related to that of others, how the role is related to practical training, and how the role ultimately contributes to the outcome of practical training. Thereafter these critical aspects were grouped into themes of variation, running through the conceptions. Consequently, a logically inclusive structure relating the different meanings as well as representing different ways of experiencing a phenomenon were thus seen as a set of categories (or so-called “outcome spaces”) that are hierarchically ordered in terms of complexity and on the basis of specific structural aspects (Sappa & Aprea, 2014).

3 Findings

The empirical data showed three conceptions of social partner role of specialists training in school-based IVET: 1) training of specialist in occupational field; 2) developing programmes; 3) training of teachers (Table 2). These qualitatively distinct conceptions were reflected through three themes of variations that illustrate analytical differences in conceptions. Further, a detailed description of each category, with special attention to the critical aspects, follows.

Table 2

Categories of understanding employers’ role in specialist training, described in terms of themes

Themes of variation	Conceptions		
	1. Training of specialists in occupational field	2. Developing IVET programmes	3. Teacher training
	1.1. Providing occupation related capabilities	1.2. Providing other capabilities	
Responsibility	Shared responsibility on knowledge and skills development	Shared responsibility: professional identity and general competencies	Greater responsibility on one part
Interest / Benefit	More benefits for one party		Distinct interests
Expectations for collaboration	Unsatisfied		Unsatisfied
			Willingness to take responsibility from one side
			Distinct interests
			Uncertain

Conception 1: Training of specialists in occupational field

The first conception shows full awareness of parties' role and acceptance of the responsibility in specialists training. This conception includes two sub-categories that distinguish between occupation related and other complementary capabilities. Each party involved acknowledges their role and that of others in the training process of student-specialist. VET teachers consider themselves as key in granting professional foundations and maximum theoretical knowledge of the subject and technology. While employers take responsibility to provide practical knowledge, such as acquaintance with the latest equipment, work environment, work tools, etc., and to provide practical skills by teaching refinements of the craft ("*various tricks of the craft*"). Share of responsibilities also occur in providing other capabilities, necessary for the occupation. The in-company trainers focus on the development of students' professional identity: "*we help to understand if this is the student's specialty, if s/he has a calling*". For VET teachers, the general (core) competencies that are inseparable from professional ones, such as *ability to well navigate the situation, organization, ability to work in a team as well as developing students' self-esteem, supporting and motivating them* – are more important.

Practical training of students becomes beneficial for employers in terms of new employees' search. During internships, they are looking for "*promising young people, who can create a value-added product for the company*". For that, employers express their willingness to invest in revealing new talents, what often means - to retrain students according to oneself. The main benefit for VET teachers - the desire that employers should provide "*what the school cannot provide*". These is the development of practical skills while working with new equipment, which schools do not usually have.

There was some kind of dissatisfaction between social partners. Employers are disappointed with school activities because during practice students "*lack communication skills, responsibility for their actions; students face with problems in performing individual and team tasks*". On the other hand, VET teachers express their beliefs that employers could be more involved in this process of practical training.

Conception 2: Development of VET programmes

The second conception focuses on the development of VET programmes, as a prerequisite for practical training of students and an area for social partners' collaboration. They do not take this part of role as a shared responsibility; rather, one part assumes greater responsibility. VET teachers take care for designing programmes according to "*the needs and requirements of the labour market*". This involves designing theoretical knowledge, plans for practical training "*covering all the subjects*" so that students can try "*in a real workplace what they have learned at school*". The employers can offer the expert knowledge to update theoretical materials:

"Sometimes we read programmes; it seems that you are reading about some ancient profession of your grandfather. What should it look like for a young person thinking about choosing this specialty? Will s/he be interested in it?" (Master trainer, male, Mechanics sector)

Social parties benefit differently from the development of study programmes. For VET teachers, the programmes developed according to the *needs and requirements of the labour market* means greater popularity with all the consequences that follow. For employers, motivation and engagement of students into learning process through interesting and updated programmes is important.

There is a sense of miscommunication between partners. Employers expect to be invited and involved into teaching process, but do not see such a need on the part of schools. In turn, VET teachers feel too little participation of employers in this process.

Conception 3: Professional training of teachers (Professional support for teachers)

In this conception, the participants are in the periphery of the training of specialists with their role almost non-existent. The participants showed awareness that there is an urgent need for VET teachers' professional development, as a necessary precondition of specialists training. The idea of taking responsibility of this part of the role is more pronounced among employers. They would like VET teachers „to come to companies at least once every six months to share experience and gain practical skills“.

The employers see general benefit for the programme development and practical training of students:

“I really see the need for teachers to improve their qualifications: when they have more knowledge from a practical, real situation in the field of business, it will be much easier for them to prepare and adjust programmes so that the knowledge provided is useful for future specialists” (Master trainer, male, Wood sector)

Teachers see the benefit for themselves and for their students:

“Teachers lack professional development, because the real teacher who teaches but does not work improves only as a teacher <...> but not all teachers improve in that practical sense ...” (VET teacher, male, Health sector)

No consolidation is observed on the collaboration level. Business and enterprise representatives do not receive a response to their initiatives, and VET schools representatives see little opportunity to practise in companies. Discrepancies between teachers' expectations to have internships in companies and real possibilities were perceived as inevitable because of the motivational and financial aspects:

“Business is not motivated to provide knowledge. First of all, the stakeholder must see the economic benefits of such cooperation and not just experience the costs” (VET teacher, female, Business administration sector)

From this perspective, teachers' expectations and reflections on greater stakeholder involvement into training process are related to the financial promotion of this process, which is foreseen as some measures at the state that would encourage initiative. The employers' statements did not confirm this idea.

4 Discussion and conclusions

This study explored how social partners in school-based IVET conceptualise their roles and what they expect from the other-part in training qualified specialists. The two key players at the bottom of the chain – IVET teachers and in-company trainers – were brought in one study seeking to triangulate their conceptions regarding their role in the training process. By using a phenomenographic approach, the study exposed different levels of understanding and different expectations of social parts involved in specialist training and how this result in either contradictions or collaboration. The conceptions in this study could provide an explanation on why the collaboration among VET institutions and business organisations have not always been successful.

There is a shared perception of the traditional role regarding specialist training. The IVET teachers and in-company trainers provide knowledge and skills in the occupational field as well as develop other competencies needed in the labour market (Sauli, 2021; Gunbayi, 2015; Zoran & Elena, 2015; van der Sluis et al., 2014; Pogorzelska, 2013; Winterton et al., 2008; Ruškus et al., 2005). In providing knowledge, IVET teachers emphasise theoretical knowledge of the field, while in-company trainers feel more responsible for providing practical applicable

knowledge. Regarding other capabilities, their responsibilities are also slightly different: in-company trainers are concerned with developing a professional identity, whereas IVET teachers see a wider context and feel responsible for the development of general competences. In terms of benefits, the positions of the participating parties are not the same - employers benefit more than schools from this particular role-playing. Therefore, they have more interests towards practical training. Where the individual parties fully understand their own role and that of other parties, there are different expectations on how this role should be implemented by other party. The employers' dissatisfaction arises on that teachers do not prepare student, or in their words, unprepared students come to practice. The IVET teachers' dissatisfaction with collaboration is more uncertain, expressed by a vague desire for "greater involvement" of employers.

At a relatively perceived conception, the social partners see their roles as developing IVET programmes (Rauner & Wittig, 2013; Nielsen, 2011) that meet modern technological, environmental, social, etc. requirements. The school teachers are more aware and assume more responsibility of this role. The employers feel themselves as in a subordinate role when expert knowledge in the field is required from them. The conceptions in this study showed that the parties differently understand their roles playing. The employers' interest is to prepare attractive programs for students, while the teachers' interest is focused on compatibility of training programs with the requirements of the labour market. However, discrepancies between expectations on collaboration arise. The employers want to strengthen their role not only in providing the updated knowledge but also in teaching young people. Accordingly, the IVET teachers are not satisfied with employers' participation in programme development and expect more active expert role from them.

While the traditional roles of social partners in IVET were mentioned by other authors as well as regulated by the law, this study revealed one more role – training of IVET teachers. Employers expressed their readiness to take on this role because they see teacher training as a prerequisite for preparing better trainees-specialists. The teachers' point of view is more formal, coming from the imperative for continuous learning that is placed for all teachers. Discrepancies arise in social partners understanding how this role could be embedded on the practical level. Employers do not identify obstacles to this process, while teachers, on the contrary, see a lack of business motivation due to financial (dis)benefits. Thus, this role is more like as "desirable" (Sauli, 2021) than perceived and assumed responsibility.

Following the research aim, peculiarities of school-based IVET social partners' roles should be identified. The context description has shown that the roles of social partners in IVET are increasing and becoming more complex. The empirical analysis of this study showed that all parties involved in specialists' training accept and assume their role, moreover - in the training of specialists, they would like to take on a new role that is not formally assigned to them. But the parties have different understanding of performance of this role that creates unsatisfied expectations for the other party. In other words, one's role is fully understood, but the partner's role is viewed through the prism of one's field.

The findings of this study linked with literature from other settings showed that there are unsatisfactory in social partners' performance (Sappa, 2014; Sauli, 2021), lack of social partners' involvement into partnerships (Akomaning, et al., 2011; Rizzo et al., 2017; Munangatire & McInerney, 2022) in dual vocational training as well. In any form of IVET, social partnership faces some difficulties. These difficulties in school-based vocational training form could be interpreted as follows. Stagnant collaboration between partners have not changed for a long time. Perhaps, the inherited regulatory role of the state creates certain patterns of behaviour at the bottom of the chain. For example, this could be observed in the new role of teacher training: employers see an opportunity to collaborate, but VET teachers are reserved – they are waiting for the state's encouraging action.

Based on the results of this study, it seems that it is important to develop connective strategies among social partners. Paraphrasing Sappa et al. (2016), this entails that they need to broaden their knowledge on approaches and attitudes of other party by thus connecting different points of view.

Finally, this study has certain limitations. The study was conducted in the schools and enterprises of one city that make the findings contextual. It covered several occupational fields, what made the analysis more general and, potentially, vocational field specificities, which are important in the IVET, were not taken into account. Future studies could analyse social partners' roles among vocational fields, for example, production or service. This study explored the roles of social partners at a micro level without considering those at the meso (e.g., professional associations) and macro levels (e.g., state representatives) who also play a significant role in IVET partnerships. In future studies, it would be interesting to collect more specific data, including those obtained from social partners from various levels.

Perhaps, a certain bias could not be avoided during the research process. While the conceptions were based on the words of the participants, these words were influenced by researcher during data collection and the interpretation was driven by the philosophies and interest of researcher. As Munangatire and McInerney (2022) note, interpretations cannot be completely without bias of researchers as they are the once who construct the conceptions. Therefore, readers and other researchers are open to scrutinise the conceptions based on the data given and arrive at a different interpretation.

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Biographical note

Dr **Rita Mičiulienė** is a senior researcher at the Institute of Educational Research. Her research interests include social partnership in vocational education, VET teachers' professional development. She is a member of the Lithuanian Educational Research Association (LERA) which is a part of the European Educational Research Association (EERA).